
INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

It is important to weigh the benefits and drawbacks of the technology before applying it to the classroom. Incorporating multimedia into the teaching and learning process would undoubtedly increase the lesson's effectiveness, but if the incorrect techniques are used or the wrong resources are chosen, the process could be stifled. The three methods for applying digital technology to create teaching materials will be covered in this article.

Keywords: *designing materials, implement, digital technology, low-tech activity, moderate-tech activity, high-tech activity, Padlet wall, British National Corpus.*

The advancement of technology gave us the chance to use digital technology in the classroom and boost the lesson's efficacy with the aid of contemporary technology, which is regarded as one of the real 21st-century requirements. While implementing a particular technology, we occasionally forget to take into an account its accessibility, flexibility for all learners and the target group, whether instructional approaches meet learners' needs, whether technology allows for interaction between learners and teachers, whether it is new and alluring enough to draw in learners, and whether it is specifically used to improve language skills. Three methods for incorporating several digital learning activities on the same subject into the classroom will be analyzed.

1. Low tech approach

It is stated that text-driven approach in materials development is considered to mean not only writing materials effectively, quickly, but also articulating and developing their own theories. This type of approach has its own framework which help materials developers to follow and create their own materials. Moreover, the activities developed on the basis of this approach enable learners to achieve interaction between the text and learner`s sense, feelings, intuitions [Tomlinson, 2003: 109].

While designing the first activity which is considered to be low-tech activity, the steps stated in the framework of designing materials are followed:

1. Readiness activities: In this stage, we tried to use personalization that assists learners to associate their personal feelings, intuitions with the content of the text
2. Experiential activities: in this stage, we focused on linking the thought and facts expressed in the text from the readiness activity when they had a chance to be exposed to the situation
3. Intake response: in this stage learners had an opportunity to use their inner speech while interacting with their classmates
4. Development activity: students were supposed to do different tasks to relocate writer`s view, and respond to it.

This activity states the learner in the center of the learning process which is one of the main principles CLT method.

Activity 1 Letter to generation (30 min.-low-tech activity)

Pre-listening:

a) Ask students to think about the year 2100. Tell them to imagine that they survived and live at that time. Ask them to clearly picture the environment: What is it like? What are the cities, villages like? Ask them about their feelings about the time they are living.

b) Pair work: Tell learners to work in pairs and describe the environment they imagined by sharing their feelings about 2100 year.

Assessment of the task: Informal. Give some feedback having listened to the opinions by supporting teacher-student interaction.

While-listening: Tell the learners they are going to listen to a poem about the environment in the future and ask them to compare the pictures in their mind with the poem as they listen. Ask them to find similarities and differences between the facts in the poems and their imagined picture.

Listening:

Dear future generations, Sorry

(The extract from the poem “Dear future generations: Sorry by Prince Ea)

Dear future generations Sorry

I think I speak for the rest of us when I say

Sorry

Sorry, we left you with our mess of a planet

Sorry that we were too caught up in our own doings to do something

Sorry we listened to people who made excuses to do nothing....

I hope you forgive us.

We just didn't realize how special the Earth was like a marriage go wrong

Like, we don't know what we had until it was gone....

For example, I am guessing you probably know what is the Amazon desert

Right?

We believe it or not it was once called the Amazon rainforest

and there were billions of trees there

All of them gorgeous and ...

Oh... You don't know much about trees. Do you?

*Well let me tell you trees are amazing. I mean we literally breathe the air they
are creating*

They clean up our pollution or carbon,

They store and purify water,

give us medicine that cures our diseases,

food that feeds us which is why I'm so sorry

To tell you that we burn them down

*Cut them down with brutal machines horrific at a rate of 40 football fields every
minute*

That's 50 % of all the trees in the world gone in the last hundred years. Why?

• Group learners into for small groups and ask them to work in group and discuss
the similarities and differences between the imagined future and facts in the poems

• Illustrate the photos on the screen, hand out the printed version of the poem
and ask each group to associate the photos with the facts in poem:

Post listening

Assign each group with different tasks:

Group A: describe the main idea of the poem with illustrations

Group B: write a letter to the future generation and state what you are leaving
them(using verbs and expressions of probability)

Group C: write a short newspaper report (of 60-80) words about one of the
distractions to the nature

Group D: Role play. You are, TV-reporter, preparing a video about life in Africa.
You are asking local people about damage that is done to the environment. Interview
them.

2. High-tech approach

While preparing this activity, the proposed framework by Motteram was taken into consideration. According to his framework, one is supposed to make an emphasis on whether a particular technology is accessible, flexible for all learners and target group, whether instructional approaches meet learners` needs, whether technology provides interaction between learner and learner, learner and teacher, whether it is new, appealing enough to attract the learners, whether it is used purposely to develop language skills [Motteram, 2011:303].

Taking into consideration these criteria, Padlet wall is used. This online tool allows teachers to prepare different tasks related to the language skills, upload, download materials for learners, to assign tasks, to conduct online discussions. Moreover, By connecting it to Corpus, learners are able to find themselves frequently used words, word collocations, grammar structures, share them with their classmates. That is to say it can help learners to learn language aspects in an inductive way. If the first activity was based on the enhancement of learner`s listening and speaking skills in collaboration, the second one focuses on developing learners` reading, writing skills and lexical resource. Moreover, teachers can easily change the tasks and make it for learners who prefer to learn independently. This means that the used technology can meet learner`s need not only in terms of language need, but also in terms of their multiple learning styles. Moreover, Padlet can be used for in-class activities or it can be utilized to be used outside the classroom.

Activity 2: (High-tech activity) Padlet wall

Ask students to enter the classroom Padlet wall

Pre-reading

Task: Ask students to watch the video posted on Padlet and post their comments on Padlet wall

What is the message conveyed in the video? Support your answer by providing the evidence

Which scene triggered you most? Why?

While reading

Ask students to skim /scan the passage and do

- Matching exercise
- Answering the questions

The image is a screenshot of a web browser displaying a Padlet wall. The browser's address bar shows the URL: https://padlet.com/xamzayeveva_mukaddasson/7f1jjoy3xz40/wish/372380169. The Padlet wall has a brick background. On the left, there is a sidebar with a 'Pre-reading activitie' section containing the same text as the main activity. The main content area features a video player with a play button and a 'BBC NEWS' logo. Below the video, the text reads: 'Pre-reading activitie', 'Watch the video and discuss the following questions in group and post your comments on wall.', 'What is the message conveyed in the video?', and 'Which scene triggered you most? Why?'. To the right of the video, there are options for 'FLAG' and 'VIEW ORIGINAL'. The bottom of the screenshot shows a Windows taskbar with the time 18:57 and date 26.07.2019.

Assessment: Formal. Check the answers. Give 1 point per each correct answer (Matching Task- 4 questions,

Comprehension check 6 questions)

Vocabulary teaching: British National corpus

A. Group the class forming 4 small groups. Provide each group with words and word combinations highlighted in the passage. Ask each group to use link provided on Padlet wall and find out followings:

- The meaning of the word
- The frequency usage of the word
- The word formations

- d) Collocations
 - e) Making up examples by using active vocabulary and expressions of certainty (must, may, to be supposed to, to be likely to)
- B. Ask each group to share their findings on the Padlet wall
- Assessment: Informal. Check examples provided by each group. Give oral feedback to each group and explain mistakes.

Post- reading

Commenting: Ask students to watch the video again and leave their comments about why and how people have to preserve the Amazon rainforest on the YouTube video shared by Padlet wall using active vocabulary they learned.

3. Moderate level of technology use

The last activity which is considered to be re-design-based digital activity. According to Hockly (2012), this type of activities can enhance learners` skill of paraphrasing, and knowledge about issues of copyright, and plagiarism, which are also important skill to acquire[Hockly, 2012:108p.].

Activity 3. Parody (Moderate level of technology use)

(This task can also be used as a home task)

Pre-task: Questionnaire:

In Group of 4 develop 5 questions which you would like to ask from World Environment Conservation Organization.

Ask each group to change the questions and rewrite them by paraphrasing

Assessment: Check the used grammar, vocabulary and paraphrasing skills. Give oral feedback by explaining the mistakes.

While task:

Share the link of the video. Tell student to watch short video on You tube about the environment problems (2 minute videos) and take some notes. And rewrite the news by paraphrasing.

Post task:

Ask each group to make the parody of the video and post it on Padlet wall. Each student in the group should watch and put their “likes” by clicking. Aware them that they cannot vote for their own video prepared in their group.

Conclusion

Piloting is the most practical application of the technology, as it canYou must address the development of the material at every stage of the learning and teaching process. By gathering information, one should consider effective teaching materials when creating a needs analysis. Similarly, while creating a lesson plan, one must consider how to present the lesson and what resources to utilize to engage learners. Multimedia integration into the classroom is a difficult process since it takes time and experience to determine whether using technology in the classroom will advance education or merely be a waste of time and resources.. The most effective way to apply the technology is to piloting which can consider whether the material you are going to use is applicable in terms of teaching methods, course syllabus curriculum principles and of course, desired outcomes.

Teachers are expected to receive positive feedback if they pay attention to each student individually, create lessons that take into an account the needs of the students,

assess the students' skills by differentiating instruction, and give the students the chance to assess themselves by working with students of various language proficiency levels. In other words, educators successfully guide students toward success. The function of these educators is that of a pursuer, looking for the most effective approach for language learners to study a foreign language over time and in a variety of settings where each learner may feel comfortable and equal to interact and learn the language they are learning.

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